

Supplementary Material

Sentinels of marine litter: global overview of plastic ingestion by seabirds

S1. Specific details of studies assessing plastic ingestion by seabirds.

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2014	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Alca torda</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	15	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Alca torda</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	12	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2005	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Alle alle</i>	East Greenland	NW Atlantic	26	50.0	Gular pouch	Amélineau et al., 2016
2013	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Alle alle</i>	White Bay, Newfoundland, Canada	N Atlantic	65	14.0	Gizzard	Fife et al., 2015
2013	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Alle alle</i>	Newfoundland, Canada	NW Atlantic	171	30.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2016
2014	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Alle alle</i>	East greenland	NW Atlantic	18	33.0	Gular pouch	Amélineau et al., 2016
2001-2011	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Brachyramphus marmoratus</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	7	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2001-2011	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Cepphus columba</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	10	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2013	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Cepphus grylle</i>	Prince Leopold Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	3	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Poon et al., 2017
2014	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Cepphus grylle</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2018	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Cepphus grylle</i>	Canadian Artic (Qikiqtarjuaq, Nunavut)	NW Atlantic	20	0.0	GITs with intestines	Baak, Provencher & Mallory, 2020
2001-2011	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Cerohinca monocerata</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	32	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2014	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Fratercula arctica</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	3	33.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Fratercula arctica</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	11	27.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2001-2011	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Fratercula cirrhata</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2014	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Ptychoramphus aleuticus</i>	Canadian pacific region	N Pacific	85	40.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	O'Hara et al., 2019

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2001-2011	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Ptychoramphus aleuticus</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2006-2019	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Synthliboramphus antiquus</i>	Korean Peninsula	NW Pacific	110	0.9	GITs without intestines	Nam et al., 2021
2001-2011	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Synthliboramphus antiquus</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	5	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Basto et al., 2019
2014	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria aalge</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	25	12.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2001-2011	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria aalge</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	37	3.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2015-2019	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria aalge</i>	South-eastern Baltic Sea	NE Atlantic	33	3.0	GITs without intestines	Morkūnas et al., 2021
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria aalge</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	61	11.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2007	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Minarets	N Pacific	30	10.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Provencher al., 2010
2007	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Coats Island	NW Atlantic	25	4.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Provencher al., 2010
2007	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Canadian Artic (Qikiqtarjuaq, Nunavut)	NW Atlantic	30	7.0	GITs with intestines	Baak, Provencher & Mallory, 2020
2008	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Minarets	N Pacific	20	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Provencher al., 2010
2008	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Digges Sound (30)	NW Atlantic	30	17.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Provencher al., 2010
2008	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Akpatok Island,Nunavut, Canada,	NW Atlantic	31	23.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Provencher al., 2010
2008	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Prince Leopold Island	NW Atlantic	50	8.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Provencher al., 2010
2008	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Prince Leopold Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	10	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Poon et al., 2017
2008	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Canadian Artic (Qikiqtarjuaq, Nunavut)	NW Atlantic	20	0.0	GITs with intestines	Baak, Provencher & Mallory, 2020
2013	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Prince Leopold Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	10	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Poon et al., 2017
2018	Charadriiformes	Alcidae	<i>Uria lomvia</i>	Canadian Artic (Qikiqtarjuaq, Nunavut)	NW Atlantic	30	0.0	GITs with intestines	Baak, Provencher & Mallory, 2020

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2017	Charadriiformes	Charadriidae	<i>Pluvialis fulva</i>	Yongxing Island, South China Sea	NW Pacific	3	0.0	GITs with intestines	Zhu et al., 2019
2007-2015	Charadriiformes	Haematopodidae	<i>Haematopus palliatus</i>	Balneário Pinhal-Mostardas, Brasil	SW Atlantic	24	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rossi et al., 2019
2019-2021	Charadriiformes	Haematopodidae	<i>Haematopus palliatus</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	2	50.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2014	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Chroicocephalus ridibundus</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	9	22.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2007-2017	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Chroicocephalus ridibundus</i>	Portugal	N Pacific W	4	25.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Basto et al., 2019
2003-2010	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Ichthyaetus audouinii</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	Mediterranean Sea W	15	13.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2003-2010	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Ichthyaetus melanocephalus</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	Mediterranean Sea	4	25.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2014	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	13	32.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2006-2019	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	Korean Peninsula	NW Pacific	2	0.0	GITs without intestines	Nam et al., 2021
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	7	14.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2006-2019	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus crassirostris</i>	Korean Peninsula	NW Pacific	70	12.9	GITs without intestines	Nam et al., 2021
2010-2013	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus dominicanus</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	19	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2019-2021	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus dominicanus</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	2	50.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2014	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2007-2017	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	Portugal	N Pacific	107	18.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Basto et al., 2019
2001-2011	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus glaucescens</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	3	33.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2014	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus glaucoides</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016

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2014	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus marinus</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	4	25.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus melanocephalus</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic W	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2003-2010	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus michahellis</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	Mediterranean Sea	12	33.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2007-2017	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus michahellis</i>	Portugal	N Pacific	124	10.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Basto et al., 2019
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus ridibundus</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	3	33.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2015-2018	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Larus novaehollandiae</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2013	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>	Prince Leopold Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	11	9.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Poon et al., 2017
2014	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	4	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2018	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>	Canadian Artic (Qikiqtarjuaq, Nunavut)	NW Atlantic W	20	15.0	GITs with intestines	Baak, Provencher & Mallory, 2020
2003-2010	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	Mediterranean Sea	4	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2007-2017	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>	Portugal	N Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Basto et al., 2019
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	9	22.2	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2019-2021	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	9	22.2	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2014	Charadriiformes	Laridae	<i>Xema sabini</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2017	Charadriiformes	Scolopacidae	<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	Yongxing Island, South China Sea	NW Pacific	1	100.0	GITs with intestines	Zhu et al., 2019
2016	Charadriiformes	Scolopacidae	<i>Phalaropus fulicarius</i>	North coast of British Columbia, Canada	N Pacific	9	100.0	GITs without intestines	Drever et al., 2018

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2003-2010	Charadriiformes	Stercorariidae	<i>Catharacta skua</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	W Mediterranean Sea	2	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2013	Charadriiformes	Stercorariidae	<i>Stercorarius antarcticus</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2014	Charadriiformes	Stercorariidae	<i>Stercorarius parasiticus</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous minutus</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous minutus</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous minutus</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	3	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2015-2018	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous minutus</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous stolidus</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous stolidus</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous stolidus</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	3	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous stolidus</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	14	7.1	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2010-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous stolidus</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	4	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2015-2018	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous stolidus</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2019-2021	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous stolidus</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	5	0.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2002-2016	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous stolidus pileatus</i>	Reunion Island or Juan de Nova	Indian	9	33.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cartraud et al., 2019
2002-2016	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Anous tenuirostris</i>	Reunion Island or Juan de Nova	Indian	21	43.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cartraud et al., 2019
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Gygis alba</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017

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2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Gygis alba</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	3	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Gygis alba</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	7	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2015-2018	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Onychoprion anaethetus</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Onychoprion fuscata</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Onychoprion fuscata</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	3	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Onychoprion fuscata</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	10	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2015-2018	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Onychoprion fuscata</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2010-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Onychoprion fuscatus</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2006-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Onychoprion lunatus</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2002-2016	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Ornithoprion fuscatus</i>	Reunion Island or Juan de Nova	Indian	27	15.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cartraud et al., 2019
2010-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sterna dougallii</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sterna fuscata</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	27	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2010-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sterna hirundinacea</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	3	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2019-2021	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sterna hirundinacea</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	3	0.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2010-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	22	4.5	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sterna nereis</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2015-2018	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sterna dougallii</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sternula albifrons</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	3	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016

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2015-2018	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Sternula nereis</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2010-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Thalasseus acutiflavus</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	33	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2019-2021	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Thalasseus acutiflavus</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	27	14.8	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Thalasseus bergii</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	3	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2015-2018	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Thalasseus bergii</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2010-2013	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Thalasseus maximus</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	4	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2016-2018	Charadriiformes	Sternidae	<i>Thalasseus sandvicensis</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2013	Pelecaniformes	Fregatidae	<i>Fregata ariel</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2010-2013	Pelecaniformes	Fregatidae	<i>Fregata magnificens</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	11	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2019-2021	Pelecaniformes	Fregatidae	<i>Fregata magnificens</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	4	0.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Fregatidae	<i>Fregata minor</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	8	25.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Fregatidae	<i>Fregata minor</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	31	41.9	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2013	Pelecaniformes	Pelecanoididae	<i>Pelecanoides urinatrix</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Phaethontidae	<i>Phaethon rubricauda</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Phaethontidae	<i>Phaethon rubricauda</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	3	33.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2016-2018	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Gulosus aristotelis</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2013	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Microcarbo melanoleucos</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2019-2021	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Neotropic cormorant</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	2	0.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021

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2013	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	22	22.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2001-2011	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2013	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2006-2019	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Korean Peninsula	NW Pacific	1	0.0	GITs without intestines	Nam et al., 2021
2007-2017	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Portugal	N Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Basto et al., 2019
2016-2018	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2013	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax sulcirostris</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	7	14.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2014	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax aristotelis</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	10	10.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2014	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Morus bassanus</i>	Ireland	N Pacific W	15	27.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2003-2010	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Morus bassanus</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	Mediterranean Sea	8	13.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2007-2017	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Morus bassanus</i>	Portugal	N Pacific	21	4.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Basto et al., 2019
2016-2018	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Morus bassanus</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	44	18.2	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2002-2016	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Morus capensis</i>	Reunion Island or Juan de Nova	Indian	2	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cartraud et al., 2019
2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Morus serrator</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	13	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula dactylatra</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula dactylatra</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2010-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula dactylatra</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	2	50.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2010-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula leucogaster</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	44	18.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2019-2021	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula leucogaster</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	13	23.1	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula sula</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2017	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula sula</i>	Yongxing Island, South China Sea	NW Pacific	5	60.0	GITs with intestines	Zhu et al., 2019
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula sula</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula sula</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	7	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula sula</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	11	9.1	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2015-2018	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula sula</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula leucogaster</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Pelecaniformes	Sulidae	<i>Sula leucogaster</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	2	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2005-2015	Procellariformes	Diomedidae	<i>D. epomophora/sanfordi</i>	South Africa	SE Atlantic	6	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Ryan et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Diomedidae	<i>Diomedea antipodensis</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Diomedidae	<i>Diomedea antipodensis gibsoni</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2005-2012	Procellariformes	Diomedidae	<i>Diomedea dabbenena</i>	Southwest Atlantic, Uruguay	SW Atlantic	6	33.3	GITs without intestines	Jiménez et al., 2015
2005-2015	Procellariformes	Diomedidae	<i>Diomedea dabbenena</i>	South Africa	SE Atlantic	5	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Ryan et al., 2016
2005-2012	Procellariformes	Diomedidae	<i>Diomedea epomophora</i>	Southwest Atlantic, Uruguay	SW Atlantic	23	17.4	GITs without intestines	Jiménez et al., 2015
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Diomedidae	<i>Diomedea epomophora</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariformes	Diomedidae	<i>Diomedea exulans</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016

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2005-2012	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Diomedea exulans</i>	Southwest Atlantic, Uruguay	SW Atlantic	12	0.0	GITs without intestines	Jiménez et al., 2015
2005-2015	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Diomedea exulans</i>	South Africa	SE Atlantic	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Ryan et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Diomedea exulans</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	5	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2005-2012	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Diomedea sanfori</i>	Southwest Atlantic, Uruguay	SW Atlantic	36	38.9	GITs without intestines	Jiménez et al., 2015
2012	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebastria immutabilis</i>	Midway Atoll	N Pacific	40	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers al., 2016
2006-2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebastria immutabilis</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	19	89.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebastria immutabilis</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	107	97.2	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebastria immutabilis</i>	North Pacific Ocean	N Pacific	18	83.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Gray al., 2012
2006-2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebastria nigripes</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	17	58.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebastria nigripes</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	28	96.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebastria nigripes</i>	North Pacific Ocean	N Pacific	29	51.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Gray al., 2012
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebetria fusca</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebetria palpebrata</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Phoebetria palpebrata</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	6	16.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche bulleri</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche bulleri</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	90	1.1	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2005-2015	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche carteri</i>	South Africa	SE Atlantic	77	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Ryan et al., 2016

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2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche cauta</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	3	33.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche cauta steadi</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	85	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2005-2015	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche cauta/steadi</i>	South Africa	SE Atlantic	601	2.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Ryan et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche cauta/steadi</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	26	3.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2005-2012	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche chlororhynchos</i>	Southwest Atlantic, Uruguay	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	GITs without intestines	Jiménez et al., 2015
2005-2015	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche chlororhynchos</i>	South Africa	SE Atlantic	18	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Ryan et al., 2016
2010-2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche chlororhynchos</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	6	33.3	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2019-2021	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche chlororhynchos</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	5	60.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche chrysostoma</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	4	25.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche eremita</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche impavida</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2005-2012	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche melanophris</i>	Southwest Atlantic, Uruguay	SW Atlantic	32	3.1	GITs without intestines	Jiménez et al., 2015
2010-2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche melanophris</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	7	57.1	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche salvini</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	30	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche steadi</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2005-2012	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thalassarche steadi</i>	Southwest Atlantic, Uruguay	SW Atlantic	17	0.0	GITs without intestines	Jiménez et al., 2015
1994-2007	Procellariiformes	Diomedeidae	<i>Thallasarche melanophris</i>	Eastern Brazil, from Peixe Lagoon (31°20'S) in the southernmost state of Brazil (Rio Grande do Sul) to the Brazilian border with Uruguay	SW Atlantic	2	100.0	GITs with intestines	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010

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2005-2015	Procellariiformes	Diomedidae	<i>Thallasarche melanophoris</i>	South Africa	SE Atlantic	157	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Ryan et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Diomedidae	<i>Thallasarche melanophoris</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	9	11.1	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2018	Procellariiformes	Hydrobatidae	<i>Hydrobates leucorhous</i>	Baccalie Island, Newfoundland and Labrador, Canada	NW Atlantic	96	87.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Krug et al., 2021
2006-2019	Procellariiformes	Hydrobatidae	<i>Hydrobates monorhis</i>	Korean Peninsula	NW Pacific	159	93.7	GITs without intestines	Nam et al., 2021
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Hydrobatidae	<i>Pelagodroma marina</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	6	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Hydrobatidae	<i>Pelagodroma marina</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	6	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2006-2013	Procellariiformes	Hydrobatinae	<i>Oceanodroma tristrami</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Procellariiformes	Hydrobatinae	<i>Oceanodroma tristrami</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	57	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2007-2012	Procellariiformes	Hydrobatinae	<i>Oceanodroma tristrami</i>	Tern Island, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	57	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Youngren, Rapp & Hyrenbach, 2018
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Oceanitinae	<i>Fregatta tropica</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Pelecanoididae	<i>Pelecanoides georgicus</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Pelecanoididae	<i>Pelecanoides urinatrix</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	31	6.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Pelecanoididae	<i>Pelecanoides urinatrix</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	2	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2011-2012	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna grisea</i>	Oregon and Washington beach	N Pacific	25	64.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Terepocki et al., 2017
2012	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Great Barrier Reef, Australia	SW Pacific	56	20.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Verlis et al., 2013
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	14	21.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers et al., 2018
2014	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	11	36.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers et al., 2018
2015	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	10	20.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers et al., 2018

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2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	8	62.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers et al., 2018
2018	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	22	68.2	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers et al., 2018
2019	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	9	44.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Szabo et al., 2021
2002-2016	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Reunion Island or Juan de Nova	Indian	9	33.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cartraud et al., 2019
2006-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	2	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2011-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Kaua‘i, USA	N Pacific	13	76.9	GITs with intestines	Kain et al., 2016
2011-2014	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Kaua‘i, USA	N Pacific	19	42.1	GITs with intestines	Bond et al., 2014
2015-2018	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	52	7.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacificus</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	28	14.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacificus</i>	Muttonbird Island, NSW	SW Pacific	40	10.0	Only proventriculus	Verlis, Campbell & Wilson, 2018
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacificus</i>	Mudjimba Island, Qld	SW Pacific	10	40.0	Only proventriculus	Verlis, Campbell & Wilson, 2018
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacificus</i>	Northwest Island, Qld	SW Pacific	35	9.0	Only proventriculus	Verlis, Campbell & Wilson, 2018
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacificus</i>	Heron Island, Qld	SW Pacific	50	8.0	Only proventriculus	Verlis, Campbell & Wilson, 2018
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna pacificus</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	28	14.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna tenuirostris</i>	The Eastern Australian coastline	S Pacific	172	88.4	GITs without intestines	Roman et al., 2021
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna tenuirostris</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	31	90.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna tenuirostris</i>	Tasmania, Australia	SW Pacific	38	89.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Puskic al., 2020

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	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna tenuirostris</i>	Phillip island, Australia	SW Pacific	26	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rodríguez et al., 2018
	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna tenuirostris</i>	Phillip island, Australia	SW Pacific	114	97.36	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rodríguez et al., 2018
2006-2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Bulweria bulwerii</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2010-2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Calonectris borealis</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic W	38	23.7	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2003-2010	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Calonectris diomedea</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	Mediterranean Sea	49	96.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2009-2011	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Calonectris diomedea</i>	Tenerife, Canary Island	N Pacific	85	83.5	GITs with intestines	Rodríguez et al., 2012
2006-2019	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Calonectris leucomelas</i>	Korean Peninsula	NW Pacific	2	0.0	GITs without intestines	Nam et al., 2021
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Aphrodroma brevirostris</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	3	33.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Aphrodroma brevirostris</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2005	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2005	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2005	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2005	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	55	85.2	proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2010	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2010	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2010	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	2	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2010	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	10	80.0	Proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2011	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island, New South Wales	SW Pacific	38	90.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers et al., 2014
2011	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2011	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2011	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2011	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	42	71.4	Proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2012	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	5	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2012	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	7	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2012	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	8	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2012	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	23	73.9	Proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	King George Sound; Western Australia	Indian	7	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers & Bond, 2016
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	7	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	45	40.9	Proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2014	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2014	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	9	77.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2014	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	11	81.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2014	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	64	39.1	Proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2015	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	4	75.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2015	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	9	89.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2015	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	12	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2015	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	54	43.4	Proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2016	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2016	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	4	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2016	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	7	85.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2016	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	56	71.4	proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	13	90.9	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	24	86.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	42	95.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	92	54.1	proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2018	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	5	80.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2018	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	23	69.6	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2018	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	33	87.9	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2018	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	113	48.7	proventriculus Only	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2019	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	33	87.9	Proventriculus and gizzard	Szabo et al., 2021
2019	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	10	80.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2019	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	23	95.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2019	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	29	79.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2019	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	117	37.0	Only proventriculus	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2020	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2020	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2020	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2020	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	0	0.0	Only proventriculus	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2021	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	5	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2021	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	33	97.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2021	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	36	41.7	Only proventriculus	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2021	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	68	87.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers, Hutton & Bond, 2021
2009–2012	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island	SW Pacific	4	75.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers & Bond, 2016
2009-2014	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	King George Sound; Western Australia	Indian	136	12.9	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers & Bond, 2016
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	213	25.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	52	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2017-2018	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna carneipes</i>	Lord Howe Island, Australia	SW Pacific	57	91.5	Gizzard	Lavers et al., 2019
2019	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna gravis</i>	Nightingale Island, Tristan da Cunha	S Atlantic	50	58.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Robuck et al., 2022
2019	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna gravis</i>	Cassino, Rio Grande RS, Brazil	SW Atlantic	13	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Robuck et al., 2022

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2008-2019	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna gravis</i>	North Carolina, USA	NW Atlantic	15	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Robuck et al., 2022
2008-2019	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna gravis</i>	Massachusetts Bay , USA	NW Atlantic	138	93.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Robuck et al., 2022
2010-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna gravis</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	16	56.3	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2012, 2018	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna gravis</i>	Gough Island, Tristan da Cunha	S Atlantic	25	60.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Robuck et al., 2022
2016-2018	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna gravis</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2010-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna grisea</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2000-2012	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Calonectris borealis</i>	Sable Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	3	0.0	GITs without intestines	Bond et al., 2014
2019-2021	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Calonectris borealis</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	5	80.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
1994-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Daption capense</i>	Eastern Brazil	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010
2010-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Daption capense</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	1	100.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Daption capense</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	7	42.9	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Daption capense</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	2	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2003	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Monterey Beach, California	N Pacific	178	75.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Donnelly-Greenan et al., 2014
2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Monterey Beach, California	N Pacific	185	98.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Donnelly-Greenan et al., 2014
2008	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Prince Leopold Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	10	80.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Poon et al., 2017
2008	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Canadian Artic (Qikiqtarjuaq, Nunavut)	NW Atlantic	15	87.0	GITs with intestines	Baak, Provencher & Mallory, 2020
2011	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Westfjords, Iceland	N Atlantic	58	79.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Kühn, & van Franeker, 2012
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Isfjord, Svalbard	NW Atlantic	40	87.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Trevail et al., 2015

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Prince Leopold Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	9	89.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Poon et al., 2017
2014	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	14	93.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
2015	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Coast of Newfoundland and Labrador, Canada	NW Atlantic	10	90.0	GITs with intestines	Provencher et al., 2020
2015	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	East Greenland	NW Atlantic	145	86.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	van Franeker et al., 2022
2018	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Canadian Artic (Qikiqtarjuaq, Nunavut)	NW Atlantic	29	72.0	GITs with intestines	Baak, Provencher & Mallory, 2020
2003-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Scottish Islands	NE Atlantic	95	92.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Van Franeker et al., 2011
2003-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	East England	NE Atlantic	60	95.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Van Franeker et al., 2011
2003-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Channel area	NE Atlantic	107	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Van Franeker et al., 2011
2003-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Skagerrak area	NE Atlantic	191	95.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Van Franeker et al., 2011
2003-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	SE North Sea	NE Atlantic	842	94.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Van Franeker et al., 2011
2008-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Oregon and Washington beach	N Pacific	143	89.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Terepocki et al., 2017
2009-2010	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	British Columbia, Canada	N Pacific	36	97.2	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2012
2009-2010	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Washington & Oregon, USA	N Pacific	31	87.1	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2012
2011-2012	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Sable Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	176	93.2	GITs without intestines	Bond et al., 2014
2014-2015	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Labrador Sea, Canada	NW Atlantic	70	79.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2019
2016-2018	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
1994-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialoides</i>	Eastern Brazil	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialoides</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	4	75.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Fulmarus glacialoides</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Halobaena caerulea</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	2	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Macronectes giganteus</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	3	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
1994-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Macronectes giganteus</i>	Eastern Brazil	SW Atlantic	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Macronectes giganteus</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	8	62.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Macronectes halli</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	4	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Macronectes halli</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	2	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2019-2021	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Manx shearwater</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	20	35.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila belcheri</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2016	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila belcheri</i>	Auckland , New Zealand	S Pacific	25	44.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2020
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila belcheri</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	79	60.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila belcheri</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	26	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila desolata</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	5	80.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila desolata</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	17	70.6	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila desolata</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	5	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila salvini</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	4	75.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila salvini</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	24	70.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila salvini</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	12	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila turtur</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	68	29.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2016	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila turtur</i>	Auckland , New Zealand	S Pacific	26	27.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2020
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila turtur</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	236	25.8	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila turtur</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	36	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila vittata</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	14	21.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachyptila vittata</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	2	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
1994-2007	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pachytila belcheri</i>	Eastern Brazil	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010
1990	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Southern Brazil	SW Atlantic	14	21.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Petry et al., 2017
1994-2007	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Eastern Brazil	SW Atlantic	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010
1997–1998	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Southern Brazil	SW Atlantic	35	42.9	Proventriculus and gizzard	Petry et al., 2017
2007-2014	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Southern Brazil	SW Atlantic	65	63.1	Proventriculus and gizzard	Petry et al., 2017
2010-2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	10	50.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	221	0.9	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	3	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2019-2021	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	4	75.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria cinerea</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	7	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria parkinsoni</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	7	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria westlandica</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria westlandica</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	16	12.5	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria westlandica</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2002-2016	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pseudobulweria aterrima</i>	Reunion Island or Juan de Nova	Indian	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cartraud et al., 2019
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pseudobulweria rostrate</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pseudobulweria rostrate</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2015-2018	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pseudobulweria rostrate</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	6	33.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma leucoptera</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma leucoptera</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	5	60.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2015-2018	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma leucoptera</i>	New caledonia	S Pacific	17	41.2	Proventriculus and gizzard	Berr et al., 2020
2010-2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma arminjoniana</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2002-2016	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma barau</i>	Reunion Island or Juan de Nova	Indian	62	63.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cartraud et al., 2019
2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma cervicalis</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma cervicalis</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma cookii</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	7	14.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma cookii</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2012	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma hypoleuca</i>	Midway Atoll	N Pacific	7	37.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Lavers al., 2016
2006-2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma hypoleuca</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017
2006-2013	Procellariformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma hypoleuca</i>	Tern Island, French Frigate Shoals, Northwestern Hawaiian Islands	N Pacific	5	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Rapp et al., 2017

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2004, 2011, 2013, 2014	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma incerta</i>	South Atlantic	S Atlantic	61	37.7	GITs with intestines	Perez et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma inexpectata</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	3	33.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma inexpectata</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma lessonii</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	6	16.7	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma macroptera</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma macroptera</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2010-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma mollis</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	2	50.0	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma nigripennis</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	2	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma solandri</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma solandri</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus assimilis</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	2	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus assimilis</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	8	50.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus assimilis</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus gavia</i>	Eastern Australia	SW Pacific	11	36.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2016
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus gavia</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	70	10.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus gavia</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
1994-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus gravis</i>	Eastern Brazil	SW Atlantic	4	75.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2011-2014	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus gravis</i>	Sable Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	84	88.1	GITs without intestines	Bond et al., 2014
	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus gravis</i>	SE coast USA	NW Atlantic	27	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Haman et al., 2013
	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus gravis</i>	NE coast USA	NW Atlantic	33	82.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Haman et al., 2013
1994-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus griseus</i>	Eastern Brazil	SW Atlantic	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010
2001-2011	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus griseus</i>	West coast of British Columbia, Canada and Washington, USA	N Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Avery-Gomm et al., 2013
2011-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus griseus</i>	Sable Island, Canada	NW Atlantic	50	72.0	GITs without intestines	Bond et al., 2014
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus griseus</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	89	21.3	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus griseus</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	15	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus huttoni</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	4	0.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2002-2016	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus lherminieri</i>	Reunion Island or Juan de Nova	Indian W Mediterranean Sea	56	79.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cartraud et al., 2019
2003-2010	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus mauretanicus</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	Mediterranean Sea	46	70.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2016-2018	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus mauretanicus</i>	Bay of Biscay	NE Atlantic	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Francoet al., 2019
2007-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus newelli</i>	Kaua‘i, USA	N Pacific	30	50.0	GITs with intestines	Kain et al., 2016
2014	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus puffinus</i>	Ireland	N Pacific	3	33.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2016
1994-2007	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus puffinus</i>	Eastern Brazil	SW Atlantic	5	60.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Tourinho, do Sul & Fillmann, 2010
2010-2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus puffinus</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	32	12.5	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2003	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	Northern North Pacific Ocean	N Pacific	87	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Yamashita et al., 2011

Year of study	Order	Family	Specie	Location	Ocean Basin	Number of specimens	% with ítems	Sample processing	Reference
2005	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	Northern North Pacific Ocean	N Pacific	12	nd	Only proventriculus	Tanaka et al., 2013
2005	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	Northern North Pacific Ocean	N Pacific	12	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Yamashita et al., 2011
2010	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	North Stradbroke Island, southeast coast of Queensland, Australia	SW Pacific	102	63.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2014
2010	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	Cape Woolamai Surf Beach, Phillip Island, Victoria	SW Pacific	67	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Carey, 2011
2012	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	North Stradbroke Island, southeast coast of Queensland, Australia	SW Pacific	27	85.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Acampora et al., 2014
2013	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	Clifton Beach colony, south-east of Hobar, Tasmania, Australia	SW Pacific	171	96.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Cousin et al., 2015
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	332	86.4	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific W	178	nd	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2003-2010	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus yelkouan</i>	Western Mediterranean Sea (Catalan Coast)	Mediterranean Sea	31	71.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Codina-García et al., 2013
2013-2017	Procellariiformes	Procellariidae	<i>Thalassoica antarctica</i>	Australia and New Zealand	S Pacific	1	100.0	Proventriculus and gizzard	Roman et al., 2019
2019-2021	Procellariiformes	Scolopacidae	<i>Arenaria interpres</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	1	0.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021
2010-2013	Sphenisciformes	Spheniscidae	<i>Spheniscus magellanicus</i>	Brazil,South Atlantic Ocean	SW Atlantic	365	15.3	GITs with intestines	Tavares et al., 2017
2019-2021	Sphenisciformes	Spheniscus	<i>Magellanic penguin</i>	Coast of Espírito Santo state, southeast Brazil	SW Atlantic	16	50.0	GITs without intestines	Vanstreels et al., 2021

